

MIMO Analysis of Port-Coupling Induced Destabilization of Interlinking DC-DC Converters

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Abstract—Stability of large power electronics systems is often studied via impedance-based approach. Thereby, the admittance passivity criterion is widely used to predict the potential destabilizing interactions between the converter and the grid. It involves evaluating, in the frequency range critical for stability, passivity properties of the converter’s admittance at a connection port. However, this approach requires assumptions about termination at all other converter’s ports, which may not be known a priori, or may change, especially when the considered converter is interconnecting multiple buses. Consequently, as demonstrated in this article, the port-coupling induced instability is difficult to be predicted by the standardly used single-input single-output (SISO) admittance passivity criterion. To overcome these limitations, this article proposes the use of multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) admittance passivity properties as a novel tool to analyze stability and develop stabilization methods for dc-dc converters. Analytical MIMO admittance frequency responses are validated using experimentally measured ones, obtained for a current-controlled buck converter prototype. Stability implications from the resulting MIMO passivity properties are verified by time domain test results, thus demonstrating the capability of the proposed method to easily predict port-coupling destabilization.

I. INTRODUCTION

ENABLED by the ever increasing advancements in power electronics, dc distribution systems are becoming widespread in various applications, such as data centres, telecommunication stations, “more electric” cars, ships, and airplanes, dc-powered homes, etc. [1], [2]. Multibus configuration of such systems is a promising candidate for achieving even higher efficiency, power density, reliability, and flexibility [2]–[5]. However, this configuration brings additional stability challenges that are not present with single bus configuration [3]–[5]. Namely, interactions among numerous converters are further complicated by the coupling between multiple dc buses through interlinking (intermediate-bus) converters, or the meshed structure of the system [2].

For analyzing small-signal stability properties of an interconnected power electronics system, impedance-based stability assessment is typically performed at a considered point-of-connection, i.e., port (bus) [6]–[8]. The subsystems seen at each side of that port are represented by the corresponding Norton/Thevenin equivalent circuits and the (inverse) Nyquist

stability criterion is applied to the product/ratio of the corresponding, *terminated* [8], impedances/admittances (jointly referred to as immittances [9]) [10]. As a more general representation, especially important for analyzing interactions between the interlinking converters and the buses, i.e., grids that they interconnect [3], [4], *unterminated* small-signal model [11] can be used. Based on multiple transfer functions that describe relationships between input and output variables at each converter’s port [11], this model characterizes converter’s dynamics in multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) sense, independently from what the converter is connected to. As such, it is a prerequisite for analyzing port-coupling related destabilization [12], and thus, for developing robust stability-oriented control strategies.

Relying on the impedance-based approach, passivity theory [13] is widely applied to analyze and prevent interactions between the converter and the grid to which it is connected [14]–[17]. According to the standard admittance passivity criterion [14]–[17], for the passive grid impedance, a sufficient condition for system stability is passivity of the converter’s admittance at the connection port. Since for a dc-dc converter this admittance is represented by a single-input single-output (SISO) transfer function, the criterion is in this article referred to as the SISO one. However, to determine the (terminated) admittance at the connection port, information about termination at all other converter’s ports is necessary [8]. A topic of vast research [14]–[17] is the enhancement of the admittance passivity properties at the connection port while assuming zero impedance termination at the other port. Still, there may be cases when the termination is either unknown or variable, e.g., for interlinking converters in multibus systems. Then, if for the analyses of interest the impact of termination is relevant, additional tools (like the one proposed in this article) are needed to account for the port-coupling related destabilization.

Instead of imposing the passivity constraint on the converter’s admittance, the so-called passivity-based stability criterion from [18] and [5], imposes it on the overall bus impedance. Since the latter is obtained as a parallel combination of the terminated impedances of all subsystems connected to the considered bus, this criterion exhibits the same, above mentioned, termination-related, limitations as the SISO admittance passivity criterion. Furthermore, neither of the criteria are applicable when, in order to achieve higher flexibility and reliability, instead of radial, the multibus system

This work is funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program in the framework of the project “IPLUG” with grant agreement number 101069770.

Fig. 1: (a) Multibus dc distribution system. (b) Interlinking converter with Thevenin equivalent representation of the grids. (c) Small-signal equivalent circuit for impedance-based stability assessment. (d) Small-signal block diagram of current control loop.

features meshed configuration [2].

To overcome these limitations, this article extends the SISO admittance passivity criterion for dc-dc converters to the MIMO one. The proposed approach relies on the unterminated small-signal model [11] to represent the converter as an admittance matrix. Its passivity properties are then used to indicate stability properties when the converter is interconnecting multiple grids. It is revealed that in addition to passivity of unterminated self admittance(s), the coupling passivity property has to be evaluated. The latter is demonstrated to be crucial for predicting port-coupling induced instability. The presented approach can be considered a foundation for designing stabilization methods that can ensure robust stability even in meshed multibus dc systems.

The article is organized as follows. Section II focuses on unterminated small-signal modelling and impedance-based approach. Section III discusses ambiguity of the existing SISO admittance passivity criterion, extends it to the MIMO one, and introduces MIMO admittance passivity properties. The analytically calculated properties are then verified in Section IV by frequency response measurements of converter's MIMO admittance, using hardware-in-the-loop simulations and experimentally, using laboratory prototype of current-controlled buck converter. Finally, the resulting stability implications in *grid-connecting* scenario are validated using time-domain stability tests. Section V concludes the article.

II. STABILITY ASSESSMENT OF MULTIBUS DC POWER ELECTRONICS SYSTEM

In this article, the multibus dc power electronics system from Fig. 1 (a) is considered. For simplicity, it consists of only two dc buses, interconnected via a single, two-port interlinking dc-dc converter, encircled in red in Fig. 1. As a starting point, the considered multibus system is assumed not to be meshed.

Still, the generality of the tool presented in this article allows it to be equally applied to meshed systems. To keep the analysis of the interlinking converter concise and illustrative, a current-controlled buck converter is used as an example. Nevertheless, the presented methodology can be extended to other two-port and multi-port dc-dc converter topologies and control methods. Though the core principles should remain similar, extension to ac-dc systems will be addressed in future works, due to an added layer of complexity in small-signal modeling of systems with a time-varying operating point.

Based on the lumped, Thevenin equivalent representation of the grid, in which each bus is represented as a voltage source in series with an impedance (referred to as the grid impedance)¹, the system from Fig. 1 (a) can be simplified to the one in Fig. 1 (b). To evaluate its small-signal stability properties and analyze interactions between the converter and the grids that it interconnects, an impedance-based approach is used. This section outlines its basics, deriving at first the converter's small-signal model, which is a prerequisite to analytically evaluate stability properties of the multibus system.

A. Unterminated Small-Signal Modelling

According to the unterminated modelling approach [11] the small-signal dynamics of the converter, such as one from Fig. 1. (b), can be characterized by its unterminated MIMO admittance matrix² $\mathbf{Y}(s)$

$$\mathbf{Y}(s) = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{11}(s) & Y_{12}(s) \\ Y_{21}(s) & Y_{22}(s) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

¹To represent the grid in case of a meshed system, additional impedances that interconnect the buses would have to be added.

²Depending on the converter topology and the state variable that is controlled, it may be favorable to use a g-parameter representation [4], [11], so that the appearance of the right half-plane poles [10] in the converter's unterminated transfer functions is avoided.

where s is the complex variable of the Laplace transform, and

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{11}(s) &= \left. \frac{\hat{i}_1(s)}{\hat{v}_1(s)} \right|_{\hat{v}_2(s)=0}, & Y_{22}(s) &= \left. \frac{\hat{i}_2(s)}{\hat{v}_2(s)} \right|_{\hat{v}_1(s)=0}, \\ Y_{12}(s) &= \left. \frac{\hat{i}_1(s)}{\hat{v}_2(s)} \right|_{\hat{v}_1(s)=0}, & Y_{21}(s) &= \left. \frac{\hat{i}_2(s)}{\hat{v}_1(s)} \right|_{\hat{v}_2(s)=0}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{i}_{1,2}(s)$, $\hat{v}_{1,2}(s)$ are Laplace transforms of small-signal perturbations of $i_{1,2}$, $v_{1,2}$ from Fig. 1 (b). The terms in (2) are referred to as, respectively: converter's unterminated (self) admittance at port 1 (Y_{11}) and 2 (Y_{22}), and unterminated transfer admittances (Y_{12} , Y_{21}). They can be determined from the small-signal s -domain model of the converter and its closed-loop control system. For the considered current-controlled buck converter with digital pulse-width modulation (DPWM), such model is given in Fig. 1 (d). According to it, (2) yields

$$Y_{11}(s) = D^2 \frac{Y_L(s)}{1+T(s)} - \frac{DI_{Lref}}{V_{dc1}} \frac{T(s)}{1+T(s)} \quad (3)$$

$$Y_{22}(s) = \frac{Y_L(s)}{1+T(s)} \quad (4)$$

$$Y_{12}(s) = -D \frac{Y_L(s)}{1+T(s)} + \frac{I_{Lref}}{V_{dc1}} \frac{T(s)}{1+T(s)} = \frac{-Y_{11}(s)}{D} \quad (5)$$

$$Y_{21}(s) = -D \frac{Y_L(s)}{1+T(s)} = -DY_{22}(s) \quad (6)$$

where $T(s) = G_c(s)e^{-sT_{exe}}G_{dpwm}(s)Y_L(s)G_{fb}(s)$ is the loop-gain of the reference tracking system from Fig. 1 (d). Further, $G_c(s)$, $e^{-sT_{exe}}$, $G_{dpwm}(s)$, $G_{fb}(s)$ are the s -domain representations of the current controller, computational delay T_{exe} , DPWM [19] and feedback filter. Finally, $Y_L = \frac{1}{sL}$ is the admittance of the output filter inductance L , $I_{Lref} = -I_2$ is the dc current reference to be tracked, and D , V_1 , and I_2 are the steady-state value of the duty cycle d , voltage v_1 at port 1, and current i_2 at port 2.

The resulting unterminated MIMO admittance matrix $\mathbf{Y}(s)$ characterizes the converter as a "black-box", i.e., it describes converter's small-signal dynamics regardless of what the converter is connected to (terminated with) [11]. As such, it allows for the converter's impact in *grid-connecting* mode to be analyzed in a general case of an arbitrary (even meshed) termination, which is for the first time addressed in this article. The additional merits of the unterminated representation (1) are modularity and scalability. For example, the extension of (1) to multi-port converters is straightforward. This may be very useful for analyzing stability in contemporary *grid-connecting* applications where such converters are more and more used to interconnect multiple buses, thereby enhancing system flexibility and controllability [20].

B. Impedance-Based Approach

For the small-signal impedance-based stability assessment, an adequate small-signal representation of the circuit from Fig. 1 (b) is needed. Using the converter's model from the previous subsection, and the grids' small-signal Thevenin equivalents, such representation is given in Fig. 1 (c). Impedance-based

approach can be applied at a bus(port)-level or at a device-level, which is referred to as respectively the SISO and the MIMO approach. Prior to explaining the differences between the two approaches, the core principles of the impedance-based stability assessment are recalled, as they remain the same for both the SISO and MIMO approach.

Assuming a stable reference-tracking system under zero grid impedance, stability of the interconnected system, such as one from Fig. 1 (c), under non-zero grid impedance depends on the product of the converter's admittance and the grid's impedance, which is called the minor-loop gain [7]. Thereby, the exact formulation of the grid/converter immittances, and consequently the minor-loop gain, depends on which (SISO/MIMO) impedance-based approach is used, as outlined below. In either case, the stability assessment of the interconnected system involves evaluating the properties of the minor-loop gain, e.g., by the (generalized) Nyquist stability criterion [7], [10] or generalized Bode plots [3].

In case of the typically used SISO impedance-based approach, stability assessment is performed at a considered point-of-connection, i.e., port (bus) [7], [8]. As such, it relies on the converter's and grid's immittances seen at that port [8]. For the circuit in Fig. 1 (c), SISO impedance-based stability assessment can be equally³ performed at either port 1 or port 2. The corresponding minor-loop gains are

$$L_1(s) = Z_{g11}(s)Y_{11t}(s) \quad (7)$$

$$L_2(s) = Z_{g22}(s)Y_{22t}(s), \quad (8)$$

where Y_{11t} and Y_{22t} are the converter's terminated admittances seen at port 1 and 2, respectively, which are given by

$$Y_{11t}(s) = \left. \frac{\hat{i}_1(s)}{\hat{v}_1(s)} \right|_{\hat{v}_2(s)=0} = Y_{11}(s) - \frac{Y_{12}(s)Y_{21}(s)Z_{g22}(s)}{1+Y_{22}(s)Z_{g22}(s)} \quad (9)$$

$$Y_{22t}(s) = \left. \frac{\hat{i}_2(s)}{\hat{v}_2(s)} \right|_{\hat{v}_1(s)=0} = Y_{22}(s) - \frac{Y_{12}(s)Y_{21}(s)Z_{g11}(s)}{1+Y_{11}(s)Z_{g11}(s)}. \quad (10)$$

As seen, the expressions (9) and (10) depend not only on the converter, but also on its termination, i.e., grid impedance, at the other port. This limits their applicability for predicting port-coupling induced instability and, consequently, for developing control strategies that would ensure stability for an arbitrary termination.

As a more general method, the MIMO impedance-based approach can be used to assess stability of the multibus dc system, which is for the first time proposed by the authors⁴. It relies on the MIMO unterminated small-signal representation of both the converter, via admittance matrix \mathbf{Y} , and the grid, via impedance matrix \mathbf{Z}_g ⁵. The resulting minor-loop gain

$$\mathbf{L}(s) = \mathbf{Y}(s)\mathbf{Z}_g(s) \quad (11)$$

³If there is no port-related unobservability [6], SISO impedance-based stability assessment performed at any port (bus) yields the same result.

⁴Details about the MIMO approach, as well as its comparison with the standardly used SISO approach will be discussed in a separate article, which is currently in preparation for publication.

⁵In addition to other merits, some of which are discussed below, this makes the MIMO impedance-based approach easily applicable in meshed multibus systems, which feature non-diagonal \mathbf{Z}_g .

Fig. 2: Comparison between analytical and HIL results for current-controlled buck converter: (a) MIMO admittance frequency response (b) MIMO admittance passivity properties. The gray-colored areas indicate non-passive zones.

determines stability of the interconnected system, where, for the system in Fig. 1 (c), $\mathbf{Y}(s)$ is given by (1) and

$$\mathbf{Z}_g(s) = \begin{bmatrix} Z_{g11}(s) & 0 \\ 0 & Z_{g22}(s) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

This has inspired us to rethink the admittance-passivity criterion for interlinking converters in multibus systems, as addressed below.

III. RETHINKING ADMITTANCE-PASSIVITY CRITERION FOR INTERLINKING CONVERTERS

A. Passivity-Based Stability Analysis

A linear time-invariant MIMO system with the transfer function matrix $\mathbf{G}(s)$ is passive if $\mathbf{G}(s)$ is stable and⁶

$$\mathbf{G}(j\omega) + \mathbf{G}^H(j\omega) \geq 0, \forall \omega \in \mathbb{R} \quad (13)$$

where H is the Hermitian (conjugate transpose) operator [13]. For a SISO system $G(s)$, (13) reduces to $\text{Re}\{G(j\omega)\} \geq 0$, $\forall \omega \in \mathbb{R}$. An important feature of passivity is compositionality [23]. In other terms, the interconnection of two passive subsystems remains passive, and thus, stable [13], [23].

The above outlined concepts, together with the impedance-based approach, motivated the use of passivity theory for analyzing and preventing interactions between the converter and the grid in the frequency domain [14]–[17]. Provided that the grid impedance is passive, the passivity of the converter's admittance⁷, is imposed as a sufficient condition for stability

⁶Inequality (13) can be evaluated using standard approaches from linear algebra to determine positive-semidefiniteness of a matrix [21]. In this article, non-negativity of all principal minors is used. Note that if the edge case $\mathbf{G} + \mathbf{G}^H = 0$ is excluded, it is sufficient to check the positivity of only the leading principal minors [22].

⁷Due to the required power conversion regulation and the system delays, converter can never behave passively at all frequencies [14]. Thus, in practice, the passivity condition (13) is usually relaxed to the frequency ranges critical for stability [14]. These ranges Ω are determined as a set of frequencies where grid resonances (or high impedance magnitudes) are present, in conjunction with the converter's control loop dynamics whose impact is to be evaluated. Accordingly, instead of $\forall \omega \in \mathbb{R}$, $\forall \omega \in \Omega$ is considered in (13). For the presentation conciseness, this notation is omitted in the subsequent expressions derived from (13).

of the interconnected system [14]–[17]. Rather than using this condition solely to determine stability, the passivity criterion is often used as a design-oriented tool. Firstly, it aims to evaluate passivity properties of the converter's admittance in the frequency ranges critical for stability [14], [17]. Subsequently, enhancing the passivity properties of the converter's admittance in these frequency ranges is imposed as a design goal [14], [17]. However, given the reasoning from the previous section, in case of an interlinking converter, the question arises which admittance/s should be passivized, either the unterminated self admittance/s from (3)–(4), or the terminated admittances from (9)–(10), or else the MIMO admittance from (1). Subsequent two subsections aim to answer this question.

B. Existing (SISO) Admittance-Passivity Criterion

Resulting from the impedance-based approach applied at a connection port, the standardly used admittance passivity-criterion [14]–[17], in this article referred to as the SISO one, imposes the passivity constraint on the converter admittance seen at that port. If e.g., port 1 is considered, according to (7) where $s = j\omega$ and (13), given that the grid impedance Z_{g1} is passive ($Z_{g1}(s)$ is stable and $\text{Re}\{Z_{g1}(j\omega)\} \geq 0$), a sufficient condition for system stability is passivity of converter's terminated admittance Y_{11t} , which, for a stable $Y_{11t}(s)$, is

$$\text{Re}\{Y_{11t}(j\omega)\} \geq 0. \quad (14)$$

Similarly, if port 2 is considered, given that $Z_{g2}(s)$ and $Y_{22t}(s)$ are stable and $\text{Re}\{Z_{g2}(j\omega)\} \geq 0$,

$$\text{Re}\{Y_{22t}(j\omega)\} \geq 0 \quad (15)$$

is sufficient for stability of the interconnected system. However, according to (9) (or (10)), to evaluate (14) (or (15)), frequency response of the termination at the other port is necessary, i.e., the information on $Z_{g2}(j\omega)$ (or $Z_{g1}(j\omega)$). Thus, the standardly used SISO admittance passivity criterion is unable to account for all possible variations of this termination, which limits its applicability. Namely, the damping-oriented

Fig. 3: HIL validation of stability implications of passivity properties shown in Fig. 2, when, in the frequency range where only the coupling passivity property is not satisfied, grid resonance(s) appear(s): (a1), (a2) only at port 1, (b1), (b2) only at port 2, (c1), (c2) at both ports.

strategies developed based on this criterion that assumed certain termination may be very ineffective if the latter changes. What is more, the port-coupling induced instability is difficult to predict in this way, as demonstrated in the next section.

Also, the SISO passivity criterion is often applied to the unterminated converter's admittance at the connection port [14]–[17]. This is equivalent to assuming zero impedance (constant voltage) termination at the other port⁸, i.e., to evaluate (14) (or (15)), $Z_{g1}(j\omega) = 0$ (or $Z_{g2}(j\omega) = 0$) is used in (9) (or (10)). This again makes the SISO admittance passivity criterion case-specific, and thus, limits its applicability in a general case. Furthermore, this criterion cannot be used when the grid is meshed (\mathbf{Z}_g is non-diagonal). To overcome these limitations, this article proposes the MIMO admittance passivity criterion, which is addressed below.

C. Novel (MIMO) Admittance-Passivity Criterion

Relying on the MIMO impedance-based approach, the MIMO admittance passivity criterion that we propose imposes the passivity constraint on the converter's MIMO admittance matrix \mathbf{Y} . Namely, according to (11), provided that the grid impedance matrix \mathbf{Z}_g is passive, a sufficient condition for the stability of the interconnected system is passivity of \mathbf{Y} . Since for a diagonal $\mathbf{G}(s)$, passivity condition (13) reduces to positive realness of the diagonal elements of $\mathbf{G}(s)$ [21], [22],

⁸An example where such assumption is often justified is the high-frequency passivity analysis of grid-connected voltage source converters, where dc-link dynamics poses a negligible impact on the ac-side dynamics [24].

for the system in Fig. 1 (c), passivity of (stable) \mathbf{Z}_g , given by (12), is, according to (13) where $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{Z}_g$, equivalent to $Re\{Z_{g11}(j\omega)\} \geq 0$ and $Re\{Z_{g22}(j\omega)\} \geq 0$. On the other hand, since \mathbf{Y} , given by (1), is a non-diagonal matrix, according to (13) where $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{Y}$, passivity of (stable) \mathbf{Y} is equivalent to (16)–(18) [17], [21], [22], provided at the bottom of this page. As seen, in order for the converter to be MIMO passive, in addition to passivity of unterminated self admittance(s), the coupling passivity condition (18) has to be satisfied as well⁹. In contrast to the SISO admittance passivity criterion, given by (14) (or (15)), the proposed MIMO admittance passivity criterion, given by (16)–(18), evaluates passivity of solely the converter, *regardless of its termination*. As demonstrated in the next two sections, this is its crucial asset, thanks to which the proposed MIMO criterion overcomes all of the previously discussed shortcomings of the standard SISO one. What is more, the proposed criterion accounts also for the case when the grid is meshed (\mathbf{Z}_g is non-diagonal), which the standard one is incapable of. Thereby, the expressions on the left side of the inequalities (16)–(18), termed MIMO admittance passivity properties, are vital to locate frequency regions where the converter may cause destabilizing interactions with the grids that it interconnects, as explained and validated below.

⁹Excluding the edge, zero equality, case, it is sufficient (see footnote 6) to evaluate (18) and either (16) or (17) [21], [22]. This is because if (18) and e.g., (17) are satisfied, (16) will always hold. Similarly, if (18) and (16) are satisfied, (17) will always hold. Still, to provide more physical insight, in this article we consider all three passivity properties (16)–(18).

$$Re\{Y_{11}(j\omega)\} \geq 0 \quad (16)$$

$$Re\{Y_{22}(j\omega)\} \geq 0 \quad (17)$$

$$4Re\{Y_{11}(j\omega)\}Re\{Y_{22}(j\omega)\} - Re\{Y_{12}(j\omega) + Y_{21}(j\omega)\}^2 - Im\{Y_{12}(j\omega) - Y_{21}(j\omega)\}^2 \geq 0 \quad (18)$$

Fig. 4: Test setup for experimental validations: (a) block diagram for MIMO admittance measurements, (b) picture, (c) parameters of the tested current controlled buck converter, (d) oscilloscope snip during perturbation injection at port 1.

IV. PORT-COUPLING INDUCED INSTABILITY AND A METHOD FOR ITS PREDICTION

This section demonstrates the port-coupling induced instability and the method to predict it, which is based on the proposed MIMO admittance passivity criterion and the corresponding MIMO admittance passivity properties. The shortcomings of the existing SISO admittance passivity criterion are also demonstrated, and the proposed method is shown to successfully overcome them.

Validations are performed in both the frequency- and time-domain, first using control hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) real-time simulations, and, afterwards experimentally, using a laboratory prototype. For all validations, a current-controlled buck converter is considered. The control algorithm execution and the modulating signal update are performed twice per modulation period $T_{pwm} = \frac{1}{f_{pwm}}$, at peaks and valleys of the triangular PWM carrier, i.e., double-sampled DPWM is used. As a standard example, a proportional integral current control is used, configured to achieve control loop's cross-over frequency $f_c = 0.1f_{pwm}$. The control system features one-step delay due to finite computational time.

A. Hardware-in-the-loop Validation

Validations in this subsection are performed using HIL simulations organized in the following manner. Typhoon HIL 404 is used to emulate the buck converter and the grid, with the circuit solver time step of 0.25μ s. The inductor current

is acquired from the HIL's analog output. Analog-to-digital-conversion (ADC), the current control and DPWM are realized in DSP TI f28379d. The parameters of the tested converter are $V_1 = 120$ V, $D = 0.5$, $I_{Lref} = 10$ A, $L = 1.5$ mH, $f_{pwm} = 10$ kHz.

At first, it was of interest to characterize the converter in the frequency domain. For that, the series perturbation injection circuits were emulated in HIL, and the responses of interest were obtained using HIL's dedicated SCADA widget. MIMO admittance frequency responses obtained in this way are shown in Fig. 2 (a). Using the measured data, the corresponding MIMO admittance passivity properties are calculated based on (16)-(18) and the results are shown in Fig. 2 (b). The traces in Fig. 2 that are obtained using the analytical model (3)-(6) are compared to those obtained using HIL. As seen, an excellent match is achieved between the analytical and HIL results.

Next, it was of interest to use the MIMO admittance passivity properties from Fig. 2 (b) to predict the port-coupling induced instability. According to Fig. 2 (b), there is a frequency range where both unterminated self admittances are passive, i.e., (16) and (17) are satisfied, but the coupling passivity condition (18) is not satisfied. Thus, if poorly damped grid resonances appear in this frequency range, port-coupling induced instability may arise, which cannot be predicted by evaluating passivity of only $Y_{11}(j\omega)$ and $Y_{22}(j\omega)$. Though the port-coupling induced instability could also be predicted by evaluating passivity properties of terminated admittance at the

Fig. 5: Comparison between analytical and experimentally measured results obtained using setup from Fig. 4: (a) MIMO admittance frequency response (b) MIMO admittance passivity properties. The gray-colored areas indicate non-passive zones.

considered port, this requires knowing the frequency response of the termination at the other port, as explained in Section II.B and III.B.

To demonstrate the port-coupling induced instability, time domain stability tests are performed using HIL. Grid resonances are placed at frequencies f_{g1res} and f_{g2res} (marked with dashed lines in Fig. 2 (b)) where (16) and (17) are satisfied and (18) is not. A transient is triggered by opening the branch with passive damping resistor. When the grid resonance exists at one port only (Fig. 3 (a1) and (b1)), a stable response is achieved (Fig. 3 (a2) and (b2)). However, when grid resonances exist at both ports (Fig. 3 (c1)), despite (16) and (17) being satisfied, the coupling-induced instability arises (Fig. 3 (c2)), which is successfully predicted by the proposed approach.

B. Experimental Validation

For further validations, MIMO admittance frequency response is experimentally measured, using the test setup whose block diagram and picture are shown in Fig. 4 (a) and (b). The laboratory prototype of a current-controlled buck converter with parameters from Fig. 4 (c) is realized with Imperix SiC half-bridge modules and the control system is implemented on Imperix B-Box Embedded Control Module. Sinusoidal perturbation is injected with another current-controlled buck converter, whose control system is realized within the same platform, but executed at a ten times higher rate, so that the high-frequency perturbation reference could be tracked. Two independent set of measurements are performed by injecting perturbation at port 1 and at port 2, as indicated in Fig. 4 (a). For each perturbation frequency, variables of interest: i_1' , i_2 , v_1 , v_2 are acquired using the oscilloscope over 40 ms at 125 MS/s rate.

The acquired data (example of which is shown Fig. 4 (d)) is imported in MATLAB where the Fast Fourier transform is performed to obtain the MIMO admittance frequency re-

sponses¹⁰, shown in Fig. 5 (a). Using them and (16)-(18), the corresponding MIMO admittance passivity properties are found, that are shown in Fig. 5 (b). As seen, a very good match between the analytical and the experimentally measured results is achieved¹¹.

Similar to the result in Fig. 2 (b), according to Fig. 5 (b), there is a frequency range where (16) and (17) are satisfied, but the coupling passivity condition (18) is not satisfied. Thus, port coupling-induced destabilization issues may arise if grid resonances appear in this frequency range. To verify this, the circuit from Fig. 6 (a) is used, and the transient is triggered by a step reference change. Converter's response, shown in Fig. 6 (b), exhibits strong oscillations at the frequency of the grids' resonances. Though the grid passive damping is large enough to prevent instability¹², an undesirable oscillatory transient response occurs, which can be detrimental for system operation. This port coupling-related, undesired behavior could not have been predicted by the standard SISO admittance passivity criterion, unless at least one of the grid impedance's frequency response was known. On the contrary, the proposed MIMO admittance passivity criterion offers a simple and intuitive way to predict it, without requiring any information about the grid. As this assumes evaluating passivity properties of the converter's unterminated MIMO admittance matrix, which depends solely on the converter's dynamics, the proposed approach accounts for the fact that the grid impedances may vary. Thus, it represents a valuable tool to predict and analyze the destabilizing effects that interlinking converters may cause in general multibus systems. Since such analysis is the basis for designing damping-oriented control strategies

¹⁰Due to C_{dc} being integrated within Imperix module, only i_1' was measurable (see Fig. 4 (a)). Thus the direct measurement of $Y_{11}(j\omega)$ was not possible. Instead, $Y_{11}(j\omega) + Y_{C_{dc}}(j\omega)$ was obtained, while $Y_{C_{dc}}(j\omega) = j\omega C_{dc}$ was measured afterwards to extract the $Y_{11}(j\omega)$.

¹¹Experimental results for $Re\{Y_{11}\}(j\omega)$ are not shown at high frequencies due to the measurement accuracy being limited by the large input capacitance and only i_1' being measurable (see footnote 10).

¹²This is due to the excessive passive damping of the LC elements and the damping dynamics of the electronic load used for experimental tests.

Fig. 6: (a) Circuit used for illustrating coupling-related stability implications from Fig. 5 (b). (b) Experimentally measured response to the current reference step change.

that can ensure robust stability of an interconnected system, the proposed methodology can be considered foundation for the latter.

V. CONCLUSION

To overcome the limitations of the standard SISO admittance passivity criterion, this article proposes the use of converter MIMO admittance passivity properties as a novel tool to analyze stability and develop robust stabilization methods in multibus dc systems. In addition to passivity of unterminated self-admittance(s), the coupling passivity property has to be evaluated, to account for the risk of coupling-induced destabilization. Analytical MIMO admittance frequency responses are validated using experimentally measured ones, obtained for a current-controlled buck converter prototype. Stability implications from the resulting MIMO admittance passivity properties are verified by time-domain stability tests, where port-coupling induced destabilizing effect of the interlinking converter is shown. Future studies will use the methodology proposed in this article to develop control methods that, by enhancing converter's MIMO admittance passivity properties, prevent port-coupling induced destabilization.

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